

D9.1 - Corporate Identity and Branding

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¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Modifications Index	
Date	Version
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06/9/2019	0.2 Updated version. All parts from the requested material for brand Identity Guidelines were included. Modified by Panos Yannakopoulos and Eleni Peditoti (IEMC).
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIG	Brand Identity Guidelines
BW	Black and White
CIB	Corporate Identity and Branding
CMYK	Cyan Magenta Yellow black
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
MS	Microsoft
PPT	Power point
RGB	Red Green Black

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Executive Summary

D9.1 “Corporate identity and general templates for dissemination material” has the objective of defining the HYPERION’s visual identity and branding, with the aim to ensure the visual consistency and the effective graphical identity of the project and to support the dissemination and communication activities.

A dedicated logo together with colour palettes and typefaces were provided by specialists from the beginning of the project in order to shape and form HYPERION’s identity and to promote instant public recognition and trigger reactions from the viewers even from the first conducted communication and dissemination activities. A set of specific guidelines is also provided to assist the consortium in using correctly all the above brand identity elements when designing and producing communication and dissemination material.

Additionally, in the context of HYPERION’s consistent brand identity and in order to keep a credible and professional “look and feel”, a set of HYPERION MS Office templates have been also created.

The provided brand identity elements (logo, colour palettes, typefaces), the Brand Identity Guidelines (BIG) and the templates that have been produced, form a complete and effective toolkit for assisting both the HYPERION consortium and external professionals to utilize the communication and dissemination tools in a consistent, effective and efficient way. The main and ultimate objective is to maximize the impact of HYPERION communication and dissemination activities and to promote project’s results towards building a solid on-line and off-line presence.

Both, BIG and templates, have been presented and efficiently explained to all HYPERION partners and have also been uploaded to the project’s common online collaborative tool to be easily accessible by all.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to properly present the HYPERION's brand identity already developed from the beginning of the project, in order to serve as the basis for the HYPERION partners for all communication, dissemination and impact creation activities of the HYPERION project.

A set of specific guidelines is also provided to assist the consortium in using correctly the project logo and produced material. These guidelines are considered also to be a useful aid when instructing typographers, specialists and others employed to produce branded items and to design and create HYPERION communication and dissemination materials.

In order to maintain the integrity of the HYPERION brand identity, it is very important that all given instructions are applied properly by all. The project communication and dissemination material and all its brand elements can be used freely by all consortium members, however all external bodies, except from the European Commission (EC), must acquire the required permission from the consortium, before proceeding with any use of the HYPERION material.

1.2 Indented Readership

This Deliverable is public, thus accessible to anyone interested.

The contents are mainly useful to the project partners, in order to understand and follow the project's brand identity guidelines and use the produced templates. Moreover, the contents will be also helpful to external specialists who will potentially be hired to design and produce HYPERION's communication and dissemination material or/and channels (i.e. project website).

2. HYPERION's Brand Identity

2.1. HYPERION logo: The concept

A dedicated logo was designed by specialists from the beginning of the project in order to act as a trademark, promote instant public recognition and trigger reactions from the viewers even from the first conducted communication and dissemination activities.

HYPERION's logo has a clear, memorable and easily recognisable visual style that gives an accurate impression of what the project mainly represents, its basic aspects and core activities.

It consists of two key elements: the graphical element and the written element.

HYPERION logo's graphical element consists of ancient Greek columns, presented as a linear imprint of the ancient Greek temples and used in a symbolic way to represent cultural heritage as well as three united leaves, inspired by the eternal olive tree. The graphical element of the

logo could stand by itself and might be used as a monograph logo in a variety of printed and digital media.

The font used in HYPERION's written element follows the modern, minimal design, harmonically fitting to the graphical element displayed on the left. It is written with a bold typeface to emphasize the strength and the power of action.

Figure 1: the HYPERION logo print and screen sizes

The colour palettes chosen, mainly consist of earth-colour variations in order to highlight the strong connection of the project to the environment and sustainability.

The logo has been produced in several formats (including positive and negative formats) for different uses and reproduction purposes (presentations, roll-up banners, leaflets, website, etc.).

2.2 Logo size and usage

The logo should always appear intact. Each element and its position in relation to each other have been carefully designed and must never be stretched, altered or distorted. When it will be used together with other graphic elements, it is advisable to leave free space within the two. Preferably to each side of the logo, a minimum free space of '1/4 x' should be considered. 'x' is equivalent to the height of the graphical element of the logo.

When placing the logo on an image, colour or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

The clear space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the HYPERION logo. Maintaining the clear space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the HYPERION logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

The minimum size has been carefully determined to ensure that the HYPERION logo is reproduced correctly in smaller sizes. At minimum size, the logo is still clearly legible and easily identifiable. When using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

2.3 Logo Variations

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. This primary format is used in every occasion except from the cases it is not feasible.

In these cases, the following versions are available for usage:

- Negative/Colour: This format is only used when placing the logo on an image, a coloured background or a pattern.
- BW/Grayscale Formats: These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format.
- BW/Grayscale Negative, which can be used on a light background.

Figure 2: the HYPERION logo

The HYPERION logo (Figure 2): full colours to be used on white background. This is the master version of the logo, which should be mainly used.

Figure 3: the HYPERION logo in Black and White

The one colour logo (Figure 3): this version is to be used in cases in which the logo must be reproduced in black and white.

Figure 4: the HYPERION graphical element

The HYPERION graphical element (Figure 4): full colours to be used on white background.

Figure 5: the HYPERION graphical element in Black and White

The one colour graphical element (Figure 5): this version is to be used in cases in which the graphical element must be reproduced in black and white.

Figure 6: the HYPERION graphical element in Black and White (negative)

The one colour graphical element (negative) (Figure 6): this version is to be used in cases in which the graphical element must be reproduced on a dark coloured background.

Figure 7: The HYPERION graphical element, social media-sized

The social media-sized logo (Figure 7): to be used as a “profile picture” for HYPERION’s social media accounts in Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

2.4 Corporate Colours

Colours are also an important part of HYPERION’s identity system. Colours create a vibrant visual experience. They make things more attractive, affect people’s mood and can even subconsciously shape action.

Keeping the project’s colours cohesive in both print and digital use (online presence, communication and dissemination materials, templates, documents, etc.), is a big part of maintaining its visual effectiveness and create a strong and consistent visual presence. For that reason and from the beginning of the project, HYPERION’s colour palette has been specified in detail and exact colour codes for each colour used have been laid out, including RGB, CMYK and Pantone colour codes.

The primary colour palette consists of four colours that may be used extensively both for large areas of colour or as an accent colour. Screens or tints of the primary colours may be used to achieve a desired effect.

Figure 8: HYPERION's primary colour palette

A supplementary set of colours has also been selected to complement the primary colours' palette. Their understated tones were chosen to work well as a subtle background behind typography or other graphics, or in other situations where a restrained use of colour is desired.

Figure 9: HYPERION's supplementary colour palette

2.5 Brand Typography

The logo typeface is Futura (<http://freakfonts.com/advanced-search/futura-fonts.html>).

In order to give prominence to the brand image, Futura typeface is highly recommended especially for HYPERION's printed and on-line leaflet, newsletters, magazines and for its web-media and website. Replacing fonts with alternatives should not be done under any circumstances.

Futura Light
Futura Light Oblique
 Futura Book
Futura Book Oblique
 Futura Medium
Futura Medium Oblique
Futura Bold
Futura Bold Oblique
Futura Extra Bold
Futura Extra Bold Oblique

Figure 10: the Futura typeface – all variations

For MS Office templates that have been already created or are about to be created such as project presentations, letter templates, deliverable, agenda, minutes template etc., Futura typeface could be replaced by the following MS Office default font families: Calibri, Corbel, Gill Sans.

1) For MS templates and publications	2) For Website and other web-applications	3) For leaflets and other material
Uppercase / lowercase 1 Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt	Uppercase / lowercase 1 Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt	Uppercase / lowercase 1 Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt
Uppercase / lowercase 2 Futura Bold – 16pt	Uppercase / lowercase 2 Futura Bold – 16pt	Uppercase / lowercase 2 Futura Bold – 16pt
Uppercase / lowercase 3 Futura Bold – 14pt	Uppercase / lowercase 3 Futura Bold – 14pt	Uppercase / lowercase 3 Futura Bold – 14pt
R105 G94 B74 R98 G144 B128 R217 G226 B82	R105 G94 B74 R98 G144 B128 R217 G226 B82	R105 G94 B74 R98 G144 B128 R217 G226 B82
Uppercase / lowercase 4 Futura Light – 12pt Black	Uppercase / lowercase 4 Futura Light – 12pt Black	Uppercase / lowercase 4 Futura Light – 12pt Black
Body Text Futura Regular /– 10-11 pt Black	Body Text Futura Regular /– 10-11 pt Black	Body Text Futura Regular /– 10-11 pt Black

Figure 11: the Futura typeface will be used in HYPERION’s website and other web-based applications as well as in leaflets and printed promo materials.

2.6 Brand Identity Guidelines

The dedicated Brand Identity Guidelines (BIG) including detailed information about the logo design and usage, the colour schemes and the typography have been produced, distributed to all partners and uploaded in project’s common online collaborative tool for further relevance.

In Annex, the readers of this document could find the BIG’s pdf for further clarification. Some screenshots of it are placed here below:

Figure 12: Screenshots of HYPERION Brand Identity Guidelines

3. HYPERION’S MS Office templates

In the context of HYPERION’S consistent brand identity and in order to keep a credible and professional “look and feel”, a set of HYPERION MS Office templates (letters, posters, power point presentations, deliverables, minutes, business cards) have been created based on the project’s brand guidelines and are available to all partners through HYPERION’S common online collaborative tool.

3.1 PowerPoint Master Presentation

A PowerPoint (PPT) Master presentation template of the project has been developed. All partners have been instructed to make use of the available template when presenting the project internally as well as externally to third parties, unless an event specifies another format (e.g. a conference template that is obligatory for that event).

Presentation Title

Subtitle goes here

Figure 13: PPT Cover

Figure 14: regular text slide, bullets are optional

Header goes here

Text	Text	Text	Text	Text

Table 1: Text

H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2, GA#821054 www.hyperion-project.eu Author, Event Date, Short presentation title 4

Figure 15: text slide with suggested table design

Header goes here

Text

- Text
 - ✓ Text
 - Text
 - Text
 - Text

Text

- Text
 - ✓ Text
 - Text
 - Text
 - Text

H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2, GA#821054 www.hyperion-project.eu Author, Event Date, Short presentation title 5

Figure 16: another text slide layout. bullets are optional

Figure 17: Closing slide

3.2 Business Cards

Business cards may be considered “old school,” but also useful for networking and project development opportunities.

Figure 18: HYPERION’s Business Card template

3.3 Letter Template

The “Letter Template” is to be used when a project partner provides an official letter on behalf of the HYPERION project (e.g. to contact other projects or networks, stakeholders, etc.). This letter template could be combined with the respective partner’s logo if appropriate.

Figure 19: HYPERION's Letter Template

3.4 Meeting Agenda Template

A Meeting Agenda template has been produced to be used by HYPERION partners as a planning tool when organising HYPERION meetings, workshops and other event types.

Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Advanced Modelling Tools.

Date	XX/XX/XXXX
Status of this agenda	(V1, V2... Final)
Location of the meeting	(Place, Address, Location Link, etc.)
Participation list	(link address)

No	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country

Day 1 (Date), Type of Event

Time slot	Arrivals	
Time slot	Presentation title or/and presentation thematic	Presenter, Organisation
Time slot	Coffee Break (if any)	
Time slot	Lunch Break (if any)	
Time slot	Coffee Break (if any)	
Time slot	Dinner (if any)	

Day 2 (Date), Type of Event

Time slot	Arrivals	
Time slot	Presentation title or/and presentation thematic	Presenter, Organisation
Time slot	Coffee Break (if any)	
Time slot	Lunch Break (if any)	
Time slot	Coffee Break (if any)	
Time slot	Dinner (if any)	

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This work is part of the HYPERION project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054. 2

Figure 20: HYPERION's Meeting Agenda Template

3.5 Meeting Minutes Template

A Meeting Minutes template has been compiled to meet the requirements for the internal documentation process so that every issue discussed or decided during HYPERION's internal meetings and workshops to be seen by the HYPERION consortium at a glance.

This document is highly recommended to be used by all partners when document and detail the course and content of a meeting and summarise its results (e.g. decisions, agreements, tasks, responsibilities, etc.).

The included sections are the following: general information about the meeting, the list of participants, the discussions that took place according to the agenda and relevant key notes, an action list for future amendments and developments and finally some extra space for additional information, if needed.

(Title of the Meeting)'s MEETING MINUTES

Date	
Venue	
Organiser	
Version	

List of participants

List of participants	
Partner	Name

Agenda

XXXXXXXXXX

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Discussion

- XXXXXXXXXXXX
XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
- XXXXXXXXXXXX
XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
- XXXXXXXXXXXX
XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX

Action List

No.	Action	Responsible	Deadline	Status
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				

Additional Information

- The next physical meeting/plenary/teleco will be on XX/XX/XXXX at XX:XX
- The minutes will be available in the following link: XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX

HYPERION's Website: www.hyperion-project.eu

HYPERION's Social Media:

- Twitter: [@EuHyperion](https://twitter.com/EuHyperion)
- Facebook: [@HyperionEUProject](https://www.facebook.com/HyperionEUProject)
- LinkedIn page: [Hyperion Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/hyperion-project)

 This work is part of the HYPERION project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

Figure 21: HYPERION's Meeting Minutes Template

3.6 Word and Deliverable Template

An official Word template has been also developed. All partners have been instructed to use this template in order to produce internal reports and official project deliverables.

The template has been developed according to HYPERION brand identity, including the project logo, fonts and colours. The template is also compliant with the EC requirements regarding the official project deliverables. HYPERION Word template is available in the corresponding folder on the common online collaborative tool. Indicative screenshots are available here below while the full documents are attached in Annex 2 of this document.

Figure 22: HYPERION’s deliverable template screenshots

3.7 Attendance List Template

An attendance list template was created in order to help partners to construct an attendance list that tracks attendance for HYPERION’s meetings, workshops and other event types in which it might be useful.

Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Advanced Modelling Tools. The **HYPERION** Approach.

Date	XX/XX/XXXX
Location of the meeting	Place, Address details, Link (if any)

REGISTRATION LIST | DAY 1 | DATE

No	Surname	Name	Organisation	Signature
1.				
2.				
3.				
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44.				
45.				

HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

Figure 23: HYPERION’s Attendance List Template

4. Notices/Disclaimer

HYPERION project is co-funded by the European Union (EU). Any dissemination, communication and publication materials (in any form, including on-line or electronic forms) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results, must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through:

The display of the EU emblem

The acknowledgment of EU funding by including the following text:

For communication and dissemination activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.”

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.”

A complementary disclaimer will be also included whenever using the funding logo.

“The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of (name of the implementing partner) and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.”

Another complementary disclaimer will be also included in publications as well as when producing a communication or dissemination material.

“Content reflects only the authors’ view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

For correct use of the EC emblem, partners or external specialists might use the following link:

European flag: http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

Annexes

Annex 1: Brand Identity Guidelines

Brand Identity Guidelines

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Master Logo

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Contents

- Hyperion logo
- Executive Summary
- Brand Typography
 - Logo variations
 - Colour Palette
 - Logo Usage
- Logo Usage on Social Media
- Logo Usage on Backgrounds
- Logo Improper Use

The purpose of this guide is to assist the Consortium in using correctly the HYPERION logo.

It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others employed to produce branded items to design and create HYPERION communications material.

In order to maintain the integrity of the HYPERION project brand identity, it is important to apply all the given instructions properly.

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Executive Summary

Hyperion's Goal

HYPERION's goal is to develop a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Reconstruction of historic sites to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Advanced Modelling Tools.

Brand Identity Guidelines | 5

The Logo design & concept

A dedicated logo was designed by specialists from the beginning of the project in order to act as a trademark, promote instant public recognition and trigger reactions from the viewers even from the first conducted communication and dissemination activities.

HYPERION's logo has a clear, memorable and easily recognisable visual style that gives an accurate impression of what the project mainly represents.

The font used in HYPERION's logo follows the modern, minimal design, harmonically fitting to the basic graphic element/icon displayed on the left.

HYPERION logo's basic graphic element consists of ancient Greek columns, appeared as a linear imprint of the ancient Greek temples and used in a symbolic

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way to represent cultural heritage as well as three united leaves, inspired by the eternal olive tree. The basic graphic element of the logo might be used as a monograph logo in a variety of printed and digital media.

The colour palettes chosen mainly consist of earth-colour variations in order to highlight the strong connection of the project to the environment and sustainability.

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Logo Typeface

Futura

Font Family

Futura: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Calibri: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv
Ww Xx Yy Zz

Corbel: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv
Ww Xx Yy Zz

Gill Sans: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh
Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Brand Typography

The logo typeface is **Futura**. In order to give prominence to the brand image, we recommend the following typefaces for all promotional material printed, for web media and all applications.

Replacing fonts with alternatives should not be done under any circumstances.

Font families: **Calibri, Corbel, Gill Sans**

Typefaces included with Microsoft Windows

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1) For MS templates and publications

Uppercase / lowercase 1
Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt

Uppercase / lowercase 2
Futura Bold – 16pt

Uppercase / lowercase 3
Futura Bold – 14pt

R105 G94 B74
R98 G144 B128
R217 G226 B82

Uppercase / lowercase 4
Futura Light – 12pt

Black

Body Text
Futura Regular /- 10-11 pt

Black

2) For Website and other web-applications

Uppercase / lowercase 1
Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt

Uppercase / lowercase 2
Futura Bold – 16pt

Uppercase / lowercase 3
Futura Bold – 14pt

R105 G94 B74
R98 G144 B128
R217 G226 B82

Uppercase / lowercase 4
Futura Light – 12pt

Black

Body Text
Futura Regular /- 10-11 pt

Black

3) For leaflets and other material

Uppercase / lowercase 1
Futura Medium / Bold – 18pt

Uppercase / lowercase 2
Futura Bold – 16pt

Uppercase / lowercase 3
Futura Bold – 14pt

R105 G94 B74
R98 G144 B128
R217 G226 B82

Uppercase / lowercase 4
Futura Light – 12pt

Black

Body Text
Futura Regular /- 10-11 pt

Black

Logo Variations

Positive

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. This primary format is used in every occasion except from the cases it is not feasible.

In these cases, the following versions are available for usage:

Negative/Colour

This format of the HYPERION logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a coloured background or a pattern.

BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

BW/Grayscale Negative Format

Used on a light background

Colour Palette

CMYK colours are used in printing material RGB colours are used on web applications

C0 M10 Y33 K72 R105 G94 B74 pantone 405 C	C43 M0 Y34 K38 R98 G144 B128 pantone 5555 C	C18.5 M0 Y83 K0 R217 G226 B82 pantone 389 C	C8.5 M6 Y15 K0 R232 G229 B215 pantone 454 C
pantone 318 R154 G216 B218 C38 M0 Y15 K0	pantone 579 R206 G224 B179 C17 M0 Y34 K3	pantone 583 R176 G188 B34 C23 M0 Y100 K17	pantone 452 R197 G193 B157 C24 M18 Y42 K0
pantone 4535 R231 G216 B172 C0 M4 Y30 K11	pantone 601 R255 G249 B174 C0 M0 Y40 K0	pantone 123 R255 G196 B37 C0 M24 Y94 K0	

Additional colour palette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets etc in case you need a small touch of colour contrast. These colours cannot replace the main colour palette or logotype official colours.

Logo Usage

Clear space

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the HYPERION logotype.

Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the HYPERION logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separated from any other visuals.

Print Size

6 cm X 1,2 cm

Screen size

310 px X 51px

Minimum size

The Minimum size has been carefully determined to ensure that the HYPERION logo is reproduced correctly in smaller sizes. At Minimum size, the logo is still clearly legible and easily identifiable. When using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

LOGOTYPE PRINT

minimum size, 6 cm X 1,2 cm

LOGOTYPE SCREEN

minimum size, 310 px X 51px

Logo Usage on Social Media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

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Logo Usage on Backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, colour or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background.

The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

The harmonious colors shown on page 10 can be applied as background.

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Logo Improper Use

Display the HYPERION logo only in the forms specified in this guide.

The HYPERION logo may not appear in any colour.

Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, reproduce, alter or distort the HYPERION logo in any way.

Do not combine the HYPERION logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

